

THE FIRST NATIONAL NEWSPAPER IN FERGANA - "SADOI FERGANA" NEWSPAPER

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Abstract. This article analyzes the merits of the first national publication of the Fergana Valley "Sadoi Turkestan" in the development of the nation, as well as articles written by the publisher and editor of the newspaper Obidjon Makhmudov.

Keywords: national publication, "Sadoi Fergana" newspaper, newspaper provocateurs, criticism, press, issues.

The first national publication in Fergana - "Sadoi Fergana" newspaper - was published on April 3, 1913 under the editorship of Obidjon Makhmudov. If you look at the pages of the press, you can see that in its time, this newspaper has received high praise for its services in the development of the nation, and at the same time, it has received various criticisms and threats.

In particular, since "Sadoi Fergana" newspaper was the first national publication in the Fergana Valley, there were many difficulties in spreading it among the people and in other issues. That's why the publisher and editor of the newspaper, Obidjon Makhmudov, wrote in the first issues of the newspaper entitled "The newspaper is not necessary and why it is necessary" to urge the people of Fergana to read the newspaper and understand its importance. "Newspaper is the livelihood of cultural nations all over the world" [1] said O.Makhmudov. He called the newspaper a means of communication, a means of knowing the world.

Progressives such as Makhmudhoja Behbudi in Samarkand, Haji Muin, Ashurali Zahiri in Ferghana also wrote articles urging people to read newspapers. O. Mahmudov, who knows the psychology of his people well, emphasized how necessary the newspaper is from the point of view of Islam. The main task of the scholars is to explain the requirements of Sharia and Islamic ethics to the people. When they preach in mosques and various gatherings, only people who come to these gatherings hear them. If these words are written in the newspaper, hundreds of people will enjoy their words, which shows how important the newspaper is, said Obidjon Mahmudov.

In Fergana, various rumors spread about the harmfulness of reading newspapers. In response to this, O. Makhmudov said that we did not know what the purpose of those who do not read newspapers is, if they consider the newspaper to be harmful, if they write to us about its harm, we would publish it in the newspaper.

He said, "We hope that they will recommend everyone to read the newspaper as much as we do, without spreading rumors".

In one of the next issues of the newspaper, Obidjon Makhmudov's "Open letter to Ulamoi Kiron" was published [2]. Because after the publication of the first issue of the newspaper, those who speak against it appear. That is, according to Abidjon Makhmudov, "some scientists object to the name "Sadoi Fergana" because "sado" means a sound that comes from something inanimate, when we say Sadoi Ferghana, we would count all the people of Ferghana as corpses!" he said. I had no intention of causing a headache by answering such ridiculous objections, but if the owner of such a criticism finds out that there are newspapers published in Istanbul, Kafkaz, Baku, and Tashkent with the word "sado", their voice will be heard. If he is listening to the sound of Fergana alone without going into it, he says, maybe he will realize that his ears are heavy. He said that if people who object to the newspaper write a rebuttal and send it to the office without spreading various incitements, we will print it with joy and gratitude, realizing our weakness.

Newspaper provocateurs did not limit themselves to spreading various things in Fergana. Malicious criticisms of "Sadoi Fergana" newspaper were also published in "Vaqt" and "Shoro" newspapers published in Crimea and the Caucasus. Abidjon Makhmudov's "Shifiyunlik. Language to the press" article was written in response to such criticisms. According to him, the author of the article published in the 1545 issue of the newspaper "Vaqt" with the secret signature of "Duochi" said that "the publisher left the service due to the fact that the publisher paid little attention to people called Ashurali ilan Nuri Usmani and did not perform much" criticized the publisher's giving free reign to the clergy. In response, Obidjon Makhmudov said: "Sadoi Fergana" does not serve those who are upset and cry when they hear religious words, and who are trying to prevent the existence of religious newspapers. If the publisher pretends to be a religious person and makes it available in every issue, he is writing a religious article. The publisher's understanding of the nation is understood by the religion and the nation," he wrote. The author also stated that he was upset with the editorial staff of "Vaqt" and "Shoro" newspapers. After all, he emphasized that "Sadoi Fergana" newspaper was sent to them regularly, and said that it would be good if they read the newspaper and then gave space to such articles. He called those who spread such incitement over newspapers "press shifiun".

Reading such articles written by Obidjon Makhmudov, one can understand that it was not easy to save the newspaper and teach it. Nevertheless, these difficulties did not stop our progressive grandfathers from working and caring for the nation.

References:

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2. “Sadoyi Farg‘ona” gazetasi, 1914 yil, 18 april
3. “Sadoyi Farg‘ona” gazetasi, 1914 yil 10 dekabr